

STANDARD COSMOLOGICAL MODEL WITH COSMOLOGICAL CONSTANT

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Abstract

A standard cosmological model naturally describes a feature of our universe mathematically. Inflationary illustration is now an important part of the typical cosmological model as it describes the early stage of the universe. Also, scalar tensor theories of gravity play an important role in constructing a competent cosmological model naturally assumes a late-time rapid expansion. In this study, we introduced the characteristics of inflationary models, Einstein equation solutions for a conformally coupled scalar field, and the new idea of a cosmological model with a non-vanishing cosmological constant.

Keywords: Cosmological Constant, Inflationary Models, Scalar Field, Scale Factor, Potential.

1. FOUNDATION OF STANDARD COSMOLOGICAL MODEL

A standard cosmological model is a mathematical depiction of our planet based on natural laws that have been validated in our solar system and extrapolations (Ruiz-Lapuente, 2010) (Uzan, 2007) (Peter, 2009) (Ellis, 2006). As a result, it sits at the nexus of astronomy and theoretical physics. While scientific cosmology has piqued our interest for centuries, we can confidently assert (Eisenstaedt, 1989) that Albert Einstein's general relativity, a gravitational theory that decided to make the geometry of spacetime kinetic physical fields that must be defined by solving equations known as Einstein field equations, was born a century ago. The difficulty of determining the solutions (Einstein, 1914–1932) that are good representations of the geometry of our world emerged because each result of the concept is a spacetime, a universe. This followed a four-step process to the framework of a typical cosmological model.

The first epoch of relativity to cosmology began in 1917 with Einstein's fundamental paper (Einstein, 1914–1932), in which he developed a static solution to its formulas using the contour of a cosmic constant, in which space has a three-sphere topology. The beginnings of accurate solutions to the Einstein equations, which provide viable scenario models, were explored in this paper. The first dynamical models (Carmeli, 2002) were industrialised by Alexandr Friedmann and individualistically by Georges Lemaitre (Uzan, Inflation in the standard cosmological model, 2015) (Dymnikova, 2017), resulting in the cosmic enlargement being determined as a guess of the equations of general relativity. Lemaitre provided a crucial step by tying the theoretical guess of an expanding universe to an opinion by relating it to the redshifts of electromagnetic spectra, and hence of pragmatic galaxies. This was eventually

confirmed by Edwin Hubble's (Hubble, 1929) observations, which began in 1948 and explored the properties of nuclear progressions and atomic in a spreading universe (Hubble law). The rule of expansion is derived from Einstein's equations and so narrates the cosmic expansion rate, H , allowing us to "weight the cosmos" in terms of its matter composition. It is based on Einstein's (Einstein, 1914–1932) introduction of the so-called Copernican principle, which states that we are not in a fixed location in the cosmos. While this hypothesis is difficult to verify, it has been shown in recent years that it holds true for the size of the known universe (Uzan J. P., 2008) (Clarkson, 2008), because we perceive the cosmos from a single point in spacetime.

In a second epoch, the features of nuclear and atomic processes in a growing universe, starting in 1948, were examined (Tolman, 1934). Hans Bethe, George Gamow, and Ralph Alpher (Alpher, 1948) (Gamow, 1948) (Alpher R. A., 1948) (Gamow, The origin of elements and the separation of galaxies, 1948) were able to foresee the presence of cosmic microwave background (CMB) radiation, estimate its temperature, and compute the synthesis of light nuclei, or big bang nucleosynthesis, in the early universe using this information. When contrasted to examination, both have resulted in theoretical expansions. It was revealed that as the universe expands, the temperature of a thermal bath in the cosmos with a black-body spectrum decreases. The cosmos has a cooling thermal history, with evidence that it emerges from a hot and opaque epoch of thermal equilibrium (Peter, Primordial cosmology, 2009). This concept has several flaws, including the big bang (which includes an initial spacelike singularity), the flatness problem (the cosmos is spatially extremely similar to Euclidean), and the horizon problem (the fact that homogeneity and isotropy thermal equilibrium, are remain as early situations and not interpreted). It's actually perfect because it represents no formation that is clearly dispersed in clusters, galaxies, or voids, i.e. it ignores matter inhomogeneities. The presence of a primaeval accelerated growth stage, known as inflation, was hypothesised (Uzan J. P., Inflation in the standard cosmological model, 2015) to overcome the problem of determining the genuineness of the early conditions.

By analysing the variation of density inhomogeneities, Lifshitz (Borowiec, 2017) constructed the 3rd and 4th epochs, providing for a better knowing of the development of the universe's large-scale structure, i.e. the distribution of galaxies in filaments, clusters, and gaps. It allows for the hypothesis of cosmic disturbances (Harrison, 1967) (Hawking, 1966) (Weinberg, 1972) (Bardeen, 1980) (Dunsby, 1992) to be developed. (Using the FL space-time as a background spacetime), in which the matter content and geometry are altered. The evolution of these disturbances can be calculated using Einstein equations. This prompted the investigation into the source and character (amplitude, statistical distribution) of the early density fluctuations (2nd achievement of the inflationary theory), which can be regarded as the beginning of the 3rd period of prehistoric cosmology. From a theoretical standpoint, the basis of density fluctuation reveals the fundamental characteristics of matter from a theoretical standpoint (Mukhanov, 1981). The dispersion of the large-scale structure of the universe, notably in the anisotropy of the temperature of the CMB (Sachs, 1967) (Peebles, 1970) (Sunyaev, 2003), can be linked to inflation assumptions from an observational standpoint. The study of inflation is a tremendously interesting area with some observable fingerprints because it demands dealing

with both quantum mechanics and general relativity. The developments in the theoretical knowledge of the evolution of the large-scale structure and observational developments led to the decision that:

- i. There could be a significant amount of cold dark matter (CDM) or non-relativistic dark matter.
- ii. The presence of the cosmological constant (Λ) is required.

This led to Paul Steinhardt and Jeremy Ostriker's development of the CDM model (Ostriker, 1995) in 1995. The community was hesitant to accept this concept until the findings of a study of the Hubble law of type-I supernovae in 1999 (Perlmutter, 2003). All current large-scale data (Hubble law, weak lensing, galaxy catalogues, CMB, etc.) accords with this CDM model, and its parameters are calculated with sufficient certainty. By replying to the irresponsive question of the physical nature of the dark sector, this has ushered in the period of observational cosmology.

In brief, we may now claim that inflation is a pillar of the conventional cosmological model, emphasising two roles for inflation in the model's construction and development. It connects cosmology with high-energy physics, according to the law (Uzan J. P., Inflation in the standard cosmological model, 2015).

2. THE VERY EARLY UNIVERSE AND INFLATION

The typical big bang model includes three significant remarks throughout the universe. The first one is Hubble's law in the 1930s (the expansion of the universe); the second one is the discovery of the CMB (microwave background radiation) by Penzias and Wilson, and subsequent confirmation by additional observers; and the third is that, based on nucleosynthesis in the initial cosmos, the abundances of certain nuclei (deuterium, He4) appear to match evidence fairly well. There are some problems regarding the expansion of the universe; firstly, the universe is so homogeneous and isotropic at massive distances, which could not have connected with each other during the primary epochs known as the horizon problem (demonstrated in Fig. 1). Secondly, the ratio of the energy density of the universe to the critical density (the density parameter Ω) is so close to 1. If the density parameter Ω is between 0.1 and 2, we get the following absolute values:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Omega(1s) - 1| &= O(10^{-16}) \\ |\Omega(10^{-43} \text{ s}) - 1| &= O(10^{-60}) \end{aligned}$$

These minuscule figures appear to be impossible to comprehend.

Thirdly, the smoothness problem, which explains the cause and character of the original density disturbances, is used to explain the lumpiness (the appearance of galaxies and the structure of the known universe). The inflationary models, proposed by Guth (Mathiazhagan, 1984), attempt to explain these problems.

Fig 1: This diagram shows the horizon problem. The big bang (at $t=0$), is represented by the plane at the bottom. The points B and C signify actions at a considerable prior era and point A represents our current space-time position

3. CHARACTERISTICS OF INFLATIONARY MODELS

Weak interactions and electromagnetic interactions work similarly in the early universe, under the Glashow–Weinberg–Salam (Perkovic, 2018) unified electroweak theory, and hence a stage change occurs at a threshold temperature of roughly 3×10^{15} K. The effort of the Grand Unified Theories is to find a unified description of electro-magnetic, strong, and weak interactions, three of the fundamental interactions. At a critical temperature of roughly 10^{27} K, the Grand Unified Theories predict that there is a stage change in the universe., with a regularity among the three interactions above that temperature. Consider the resemblance between the freezing of water and the freezing of ice. When water is in the liquid stage, rotational regularity exists on the surface of water. However, when ice is produced, this regularity is interrupted or lost since ice crystals have specific directions. Again, the liquids in distinct parts continue to freeze autonomously of one another along various crystal axes, and when the entire surface of the liquid has frozen, defects at the interfaces of the various segments become visible. Similarly, in the early cosmos, the three interactions were regular above or around 10^{27} K, but below this temperature, the regularity was broken. When water freezes into crystal ice, the logical regularity is lost or disrupted in different parts of the ice, which can be measured using parameters. As the symmetry of the liquid is broken, these parameters assume various values as they freeze in various parts of the liquid. Similarly, the acquisition of specific non-vanishing parameters recognized as Higgs fields can be used to describe the way in which the evident regularity among the 3 interactions is lost. The regularity is obvious while the Higgs fields have the value zero; once one of its Higgs fields must become non-zero, it is abruptly broken. Clearly, some flaws persist at the boundary of distinct areas when freezing water; symmetry is crushed in various parameters, that is, by obtaining separate value systems for the Higgs fields. Domain walls are two-dimensional point-like flaws found in magnetic monopoles. A single defect should not be considered to work out since it is not significantly greater than the horizon distance at the time, thus a minimum number of defects should be considered, which are expected to be highly enormous and stable. Monopoles, for example, have a mass of around

1016 times that of a proton. As a result, there would be so many faults that the universe's following evolution would be sped up, and the 3K background radiation would be reached in a few tens of thousands of years rather than ten billion years after the big bang. As a result, the Grand Unified Theories' prophecy appears to contradict the conventional model.

Fig 2: Potential (A possible form for the scalar field in Equation 15)

Fig 3: Potential (Other possible form for the scalar field in Equation 16)

Because the standard and inflationary models are identical in terms of our observable world after the first 10^{-34} seconds or so, none of the standard model's accomplishments are influenced by inflationary models. Guth's inflationary model (Mathiazhagan, 1984) had several drawbacks. We will be concerned about the 'new inflation' condition on our own (Linde, 1982) (Albrecht, 1982). For easiness let us consider a single Higgs field as a scalar field, ϕ . Potential energy, the possible forms of this field, is designated in Figs. 2 and 3.

Consider the characteristics of the potential as shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The system is in equilibrium if the potential has two stationary points of $\phi=0$ and $\phi=\sigma$. The potential stagnant states are referred to as 'vacuum' situations. In Fig. 2, the value of the stationary condition at is higher than that of the stationary condition at $\phi=\sigma$. There may be a case when the system is 'stuck' in the stationary condition at $\phi=0$ and is unable to switch to the stationary condition at $\phi=\sigma$ for the cause of the potential blockage, despite the fact that has an inferior energy. The state is referred to as a 'false vacuum,' whereas the condition $\phi=0$ is referred to as the 'real vacuum,' in this situation.

If we compare the Higgs field to the inflation and very early universe, the state $\phi=\sigma$ is more favourable in the Higgs field, which is similar to the case of critical temperature of 10^{27} K in the very early universe and inflation.

The condition in Fig.2 leads to issues (significant changes). However, in Fig.4, the issues are avoided, so we'll stick with the latter arrangement for the rest of the story.

Fig 4: This diagram illustrates the evolution of the universe's R (scale factor) and T (temperature) in both standard and inflationary models. The standard model is always adiabatic ($RT \approx \text{constant}$) except for small deviations (when particle-antiparticle pairs annihilate), but inflationary models experience a very non-adiabatic event about 10^{-34} s or so, after which they are adiabatic (Turner, 1985)

Since the inflationary models exhibit the same behaviour as the standard model for $t=10^{-32}$ s or so, they include, for the visible universe, all predictions of the standard models. The inflationary theories are essentially different from roughly 10^{-34} to 10^{-32} s.

Following that, the story is similar to the standard model, with the major difference being that the early area was within a horizon distance and have similar temperatures and had time to standardise, etc., whereas after inflation, the entire observable universe can remain within such a region, with the goal of the horizon problem not ascending. Let's take a closer look at this, bearing the Higgs potential of Fig.3 in mind.

Consider the Einstein's equations

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = T_{\mu\nu} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Here $T_{\mu\nu}$ signifies the energy-momentum tensor. For the standard model, however, contributions to $T_{\mu\nu}$ from all potential fields must be considered.

For the very early universe, the stage transition into the theory can be labelled by incorporating a scalar Higgs field. Due to the Higgs field, we can add an supplementary energy-momentum tensor $T'_{\mu\nu}$ to the existing energy-momentum tensor in (1), $R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = T_{\mu\nu} + 8\pi G/c^4 T'_{\mu\nu}$.

A scalar field was suggested by Lagrangian as the basis of this additional energy-momentum tensor,

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu \phi \partial^\mu \phi - V(\phi) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

It is well known (Shirkov D. V., 2009) that the energy-momentum tensor related with a Lagrangian L for a scalar field is defined by

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \phi^\mu} \phi_{;\nu} - g_{\mu\nu} L \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

By substituting (2) it becomes,

$$T'_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - g_{\mu\nu} L = \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - g_{\mu\nu} \left[\frac{1}{2} \partial_\sigma \phi \partial^\sigma \phi - V(\phi) \right] \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

The energy-momentum tensor $T^{\mu\nu} = (s + p) u^\mu u^\nu - pg^{\mu\nu}$ (for a perfect fluid) can be written as following:

$$T_\mu^\nu = \text{diag} (\epsilon, -p, -p, -p) \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Which is in the diagonal matrix form.

We now inscribing the tensor $T'_{\mu\nu}$, and assuming the scalar field $\phi(t)$ in as (5), it becomes

$$T_\mu^{\prime\nu} = \text{diag} (\epsilon', -p', -p', -p') \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

From equation (4) we find the relations for p' , ε' as below:

$$p' = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi); \dot{\phi} \equiv \partial\phi/\partial t; \varepsilon' = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi) \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

Now putting $\varepsilon = \varepsilon + \varepsilon'$, and $p = p + p'$ (given by (7)), In the cosmic condition with the Higgs field ϕ , the updated Einstein equations are

$$\left(\frac{\dot{R}}{R}\right)^2 \equiv H^2 = (8\pi G/3) (\varepsilon + \varepsilon') \dots \dots \dots (8a)$$

$$2\ddot{R}/R + H^2 = -8\pi G (p + p') \dots \dots \dots (8b)$$

Here ε' , p' are in terms of ϕ which is given by (7).

Now considering the condition in the very initial universe while the temperature is more than 10^{27} K, we can see from (7) that ε' has the constant value $V(0)$ at $\phi = 0$. Then again, if we undertake the equation of state in radiation, we realize that ε behaves like t^{-2} and R behaves like $t^{1/2}$. Thus, we get

$$\left(\frac{\dot{R}}{R}\right)^2 = (8\pi G/3) V(0) \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

and by solving

$$R = \exp(\zeta t), \quad \zeta^2 = (8\pi G/3) V(0) \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

where $V(0) > 0$, as in Figs. 3 and 4. Thus the scale factor R undertakes exponential expansion like de Sitter space.

In modified Einstein's equations, if we set $k = p = \varepsilon = 0$, we get for $c = 1$:

$$\left(\frac{\dot{R}}{R}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{3} \Lambda \dots \dots \dots (11a)$$

$$2\ddot{R}/R + \left(\frac{\dot{R}}{R}\right)^2 = \Lambda \dots \dots \dots (11b)$$

That means (11a) and (11b) are satisfied by

$$R = \exp\left(\frac{1}{3} \Lambda\right)^{1/2} t \quad (12)$$

The cosmological constant is positive (by assumption).

The de Sitter universe has a non-trivial scale factor and is known as model (12) (with $k = 0$). Equation (12) represents the same behaviour as (10) and follows the steady state universe technique (Bondi, 1948).

We obtain the Einstein equations with zero pressure and density the cosmological constant, $\Lambda = 8\pi G V(0)$, when compared to the energy-momentum tensor $T'_{\mu\nu}$ of the scalar field immediately after the commencement of the stage transition and when $\phi=0$, the energy-momentum tensor

$T_{\mu\nu}$ of the cosmic fluid can be discarded. The scalar field dominates, despite the fact that it has begun to vary from zero (using (7) and (8a)).

$$\left(\frac{\dot{R}}{R}\right)^2 \equiv H^2 = (8\pi G/3) \left[\frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi)\right] \dots\dots\dots (13)$$

For the Friedmann models, considering the divergence of the energy–momentum tensor be zero we can write:

$$\varepsilon + 3(p + \varepsilon)\frac{\dot{R}}{R} = 0.$$

Now replacing ε, p by ε', p' and cancelling a factor ϕ from equation (7) it becomes

$$\ddot{\phi} + 2H\dot{\phi} + v'(\phi) = 0, V \equiv dV/d\phi. \dots\dots\dots (14)$$

Equations (13) and (14) signify the equations which rule the evolution of the scalar factor and scale field. In general, accurate solutions for any sensible version of the potential $V(\phi)$ are difficult to get. (15) and (16) below, respectively, yield the forms seen in Figs. 3 and 4:

$$V(\phi) = \lambda_0 \phi^2 + \lambda_1 \phi^3 + \lambda_2 \phi^4 + V_0 \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

$$V(\phi) = \lambda (\phi^2 - \sigma^2)^2 \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

For appropriate values of the constants $\lambda_0, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, V_0, \lambda, \sigma$.

4. CONFORMALLY COUPLED SCALAR FIELD SOLUTIONS

Consider the equations resulting from the action (Chubaryan, 2009) (Staniukovich, 1983) (Bronnikov, 2002)

$$S = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{6}\phi^2 R + \partial^\mu \phi \partial_\mu \phi - 2\Lambda\right) \right] \dots\dots\dots (17)$$

where $R = g^{\alpha\beta} R_{\alpha\beta}$ and the definitive of the metric tensor is g . The field equations found from the stationary action (17) under variation of ϕ are

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{6}\phi^2\right) \left(R_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\alpha\beta}\right) + T_{\alpha\beta} + \Lambda g_{\alpha\beta} = 0 \dots\dots\dots (18)$$

$$\text{and } \square\phi + \frac{1}{6}R\phi = 0 \dots\dots\dots(19)$$

$$\text{where, } T_{\alpha\beta} = \left[\phi_{;\alpha}\phi_{;\beta} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\alpha\beta}\phi_{;\gamma}\phi^{;\gamma} + \frac{1}{6}g_{\alpha\beta}\square(\phi^2) - \frac{1}{6}\phi^2_{;\alpha\beta} \right] \dots\dots\dots(20)$$

$$\text{and } \square\phi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}}\partial_\alpha(\sqrt{-g}g^{\alpha\beta}\partial_\beta\phi) \dots\dots\dots(21)$$

The Bianchi Identities

$$\left(R_{\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\alpha\beta}\right)_{;\beta} = 0 \dots\dots\dots(22)$$

From (18) we get

$$\left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{6} \phi^2\right)^{-1} (T_{\alpha\beta} + \Lambda g_{\alpha\beta}) \right]_{;\beta} = 0 \dots \dots \dots (23)$$

Now considering the space-time Robertson-walker metric (Islam, 2002), solving these field equations in this case, $ds^2 = g_{\alpha\beta} dx^\alpha dx^\beta$

$$= dt^2 - a^2(t)[(1 - k\gamma^2)^{-1} d\gamma^2 + \gamma^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2)] \dots \dots \dots (24)$$

Here $k \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$, the curvature exponent of the homogeneous hypersurfaces. To share the uniformity of the space time, we will only use the scalar field $\phi = \phi(t)$.

$$R - 4\Lambda = 0 \dots \dots \dots (25)$$

$$(\square + \frac{2}{3}\Lambda)\phi = 0 \dots \dots \dots (26)$$

To determine a complete solution for $a(t)$ and $\phi(t)$, Equation (25) and (26) are sufficient.

In case of space time (24) we can write the above two in the form,

$$6 \left[\frac{1}{a} \frac{d^2 a}{dt^2} + \frac{1}{a^2} \left(\frac{da}{dt} \right)^2 + \frac{k}{a^2} \right] - 4\Lambda = 0 \dots \dots \dots (27)$$

$$\text{And } \frac{d^2 \phi}{dt^2} + \frac{3}{a} \frac{da}{dt} \frac{d\phi}{dt} + \frac{2}{3} \Lambda \phi = 0 \dots \dots \dots (28)$$

For particular cases, explicit form of $\phi(t)$ can be obtained. Choose $k = 0, \Lambda > 0, G_1 = 1, G_2 = 0$.

$$\text{Then, } a(t) = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4\Lambda}} \exp^{\sqrt{\Lambda/3}t} \dots \dots \dots (29)$$

$$\text{And, } \phi(t) = \frac{1}{2} \phi_0 \left[e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t} + e^{-2\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t} \right] \dots \dots \dots (30)$$

From equation (14) we get,

$$\ddot{\phi} + 2H\dot{\phi} + v'(\phi) = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow 2H\dot{\phi} + v'(\phi) = 0 \text{ [For conservation } \ddot{\phi} = 0 \text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow 2 \frac{\dot{R}}{R} \dot{\phi} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \{ \lambda(\phi^2 - \sigma^2)^2 \} = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow R(t) = R_0 \exp \left[\frac{6\lambda}{\Lambda} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{32} + \sigma^2 \right) \ln \left(e^{\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t} + 2 \right) - \frac{1}{32} \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}} t - \frac{1}{16} e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t} - \frac{7}{16} e^{-2\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t} - \frac{5}{12} e^{-3\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t} - \frac{1}{8} e^{-4\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t} - \sigma^2 e^{\sqrt{\frac{\Lambda}{3}}t} \right\} \right] \dots (31)$$

When field theory implies that we should anticipate $\Lambda \sim 1$, the observable cosmological constant in our world is so small, $|\Delta| \ll 1$, that it may potentially be zero, making the cosmological constant the prevalent gravitational definitive of the universe on all scales. The cosmological constant can be successfully concealed from investigation if there is only one conformally connected scale field in our universe, as long as the other squatter

fields collaborate to diminish its impact on space-time geometry. In the last equation (31), we have calculated the de-Sitter like expansion, which is called inflation.

5. CONCLUSION AND GENERIC PREDICTIONS

In conclusion, the standard model with cosmological constants has sturdy assumptions that are self-governing of their specific application. The remarkable universe is homogeneous and isotropic, which can be described by R-W space time and inflation erases any classical inhomogeneities. Grand Unified theories predict that the cosmos goes through a stage transition at 10^{27} K and that above that temperature, there is a regularity among the 3 interactions (electromagnetic, weak, and strong interactions), which appears to contradict the standard model. The inflationary models have little effect on the standard model's accomplishments since, beyond the first 10^{-34} seconds or so, the two models are identical in terms of our observable universe. Since inflationary models exhibit the same behaviour over $t=10^{-32}$ s or so, they incorporate all the predictions of standard models regarding physical universe. The inflationary theories are essentially different from roughly 10^{-34} to 10^{-32} s. The standard model with inflation is connected to particle physics (Higgs field). The standard model with a cosmological constant is connected with conformally coupled scalar field solutions. A cosmological constant can appear in different standard models with different contexts. On account of appearance of the Higgs field, which is described by a scalar field here, a de Sitter-like exponential expansion (in equation (31)) may occur at the start of the stage changeover.

Still, more questions need to be answered. To spread the study, can we rebuild the more dimensional potential of inflation? Why is the observable cosmological constant so small? Can one construct a standard model without a scalar field? Is a standard model always connected with an inflationary model?

If we determine the answers to the above questions, we can draw a crossroads between cosmology and theoretical physics by constructing new models.

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